

Features of mobile health applications (mHealth apps) for asthma

Petar Nikolov^{1,2}

¹ Faculty of Pharmacy, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

² Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics, Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”, Sofia, Bulgaria

³ Research Institute of Innovative Medical Sciences, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Guenka Petrova (gpetrova@pharmfac.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 26 November 2025 ♦ Accepted 4 January 2026 ♦ Published 27 January 2026

Citation: Nikolov P, Petrova G (2026) Features of mobile health applications (mHealth apps) for asthma. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e180488>

Abstract

Objective: Mobile health applications (mHealth apps) can support effective asthma self-management interventions, improving patients' quality of life while reducing costs for healthcare systems. This article aims to identify trends in app features relevant to the future development of reliable mHealth asthma support applications that can meet the challenges of the new century.

Methods: The search of the PubMed database was performed during August–September 2025. The database was searched electronically using the following keywords: digital AND asthma AND apps. Thirty review articles and international studies were included. The studies encompassed the period from 2015 to September 2025. Only articles available in the English language were included.

Results: All selected apps were compared across categories such as availability for unrestricted use, functionality and design, ease of use, and information management and medical accuracy. Features preferred by asthma and allergy patients were also reviewed, including guidance for emergency situations, asthma action plans, and notifications from clinics. Despite the wide variety of medical apps available, only a limited number have been tested in clinical environments, and few have been translated into languages other than English.

Conclusion: mHealth apps have considerable potential for asthma self-management not only in adults but also in children, and they can improve quality of life and symptom control compared with conventional treatment methods. App design, maintenance, and update practices vary widely across apps and platforms. This article will assist in identifying apps that are most suitable for specific user groups and may help guide the future development of robust and easy-to-use mHealth apps for asthma management.

Keywords

apps, asthma, digital health, mobile health, smartphone

Introduction

Asthma is a chronic condition that affects 300 million people worldwide. It cannot be cured completely, and the best option for patients is reliable asthma management to improve their quality of life (Al-Nawayseh et al. 2021). The Global Initiative for

Asthma (GINA), which is the leading guideline for asthma management, included several new recommendations in 2024 (GINA 2024). The first recommendation is shifting away from short-acting beta-agonist (SABA)-only rescue inhalers to inhaled corticosteroid (ICS)-containing relievers. The second is to personalize treatment by creating written action plans, checking

regular inhaler use, addressing comorbidities, and managing triggers from all causes.

Individuals with asthma are increasingly turning to mobile health to help manage their disease (Wu et al. 2015). Many mobile health applications (mHealth apps) are available and have the potential to improve chronic condition management, but the development and use of mHealth apps for asthma management have risen dramatically over the past decade, and the apps vary widely in their content and features (Camacho-Rivera et al. 2020). It is therefore necessary to examine the preferences of users of publicly available apps. Of the available mHealth apps, many have low usability, do not provide sufficient clinical utility, or patients quickly lose interest after using them several times (Rudin et al. 2017). In addition, mHealth apps can support better disease control in compliance with GINA recommendations.

Based on one of our previous studies (Nikolov et al. 2025) on technological and digital innovations in improving adherence to asthma medication therapy, which demonstrated that digital innovations such as electronic platforms, apps, telemonitoring, and games provide more opportunities to improve patient adherence, we now take a closer look at mobile apps for asthma management, as they represent a form of support that many asthma patients need.

Different categories of asthma apps and their functions, as well as patients' and clinicians' preferences, have

been previously explored, and this article aims to identify trends in features for the future development of reliable apps that will meet the challenges of the new century.

Methodology

We performed a literature search in the PubMed database. PubMed was used because it systematizes publications from medical journals. Our main focus was on articles describing desired features in asthma app development and articles exploring medical interventions associated with asthma apps.

The PubMed database was searched during August–September 2025 using the following keywords: digital AND asthma AND apps.

Review articles and international studies were included. The studies encompassed the period from 2015 to September 2025. Only articles available in the English language were included.

Excluded articles are those that focus on other diseases or report results of asthma therapy without exploring digital interventions. In total, 404 articles were reviewed, and out of these, 280 were excluded. Full texts of 124 articles were examined, but after a second revision, 89 were excluded and 35 were left for analysis. The PRISMA flow diagram shows the search process (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram of search.

Results

As new technologies develop faster than expected, mHealth apps and their features should be reviewed periodically to determine whether they respond to recent advances in science and patient needs. Selected articles are described in this work according to available features and probable improvements based on authors' opinions or technological advancements. We identified features that patients and physicians would like to have in asthma apps (Kagen et al. 2019; Hui et al. 2020).

Artificial intelligence improvement in mHealth apps

We identified one article (Kowatsch et al. 2024) describing the Max asthma app, in which patients can choose gender-specific characters of a conversational agent, male or female, which becomes a digital assistant through the app. Virtual assistants in the form of conversational agents created using artificial intelligence (AI) can provide more reliable navigation through an app. With the rapid development of technology, it would be beneficial for most apps to support such virtual assistants in the future.

Only one study identified a mobile app developed to teach inhaler device use to healthcare professionals by recreating three-dimensional models of different types of inhalers and transferring the steps of inhaler use onto a mobile phone device (Puah et al. 2022). This is a promising technology because future medical education will require more complex models and constructions that cannot be adequately presented using standard methods.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, when people had limited access to healthcare specialists, the popularity of telemedicine increased and played a very important role in connecting patients with clinicians. Currently, its demand is becoming even higher because it facilitates communication between doctors and patients (Kvedarienė et al. 2022). From this perspective, new mHealth app features related to remote consultations raise concerns regarding whether this represents a benefit or a burden for the healthcare system, as it may generate large volumes of internet traffic and increase demands on healthcare specialists.

One article describes the ASTHMAXcel Voice app, which records voice biomarkers and detects respiratory dysfunction using machine learning techniques (Lee et al. 2025). In another study, the AIRDOC mobile app enables the recording of patients' lung sounds, which may represent a promising technology (Ferreira-Cardoso et al. 2021; Santos-Silva et al. 2024). These advanced technologies allow early detection of asthma exacerbation periods and generate large volumes of health data to identify early signs of health risks. If such data are transmitted to cloud servers for analysis, they should be adequately protected against data breaches and cyberattacks.

Respiratory sounds recorded using mobile apps and vocal markers analyzed by AI-based machine learning algorithms may assist physicians in diagnosing asthma (Paoletti et al. 2025). However, this represents only the beginning of noninvasive procedure development.

These approaches provide cost-effective analytical methods, although economic considerations are not the most important factor. Patients with chronic diseases such as asthma require frequent medical procedures, which can be stressful and negatively affect health, whereas non-invasive methods offer a significantly different experience.

Functionalities that are missing or limited in mHealth apps

Another tendency of the new century is population migration and the formation of different social groups. In rural areas, mHealth apps are bringing medical services to people who previously did not have access to healthcare. According to a survey (Mirk et al. 2017), many individuals lack sufficient digital health literacy. In the future, educational programs and digital interventions could be implemented in less populated regions.

We did not identify articles focusing on people with disabilities, although this group is expected to grow and may experience chronic diseases such as asthma. This could add a significant burden to existing disabilities. As emphasized in previous studies (Peters et al. 2017; Andreoni et al. 2025), participatory design is essential in asthma app development, and it is becoming increasingly important for people with disabilities to participate in the creation of mHealth asthma apps.

Despite the wide variety of mHealth apps, relatively few are designed specifically for children. Kim et al. (2022) described an app for children that measures indoor air quality, while Iio et al. (2020, 2022) reported a successful Japanese app designed for infants, toddlers, and school-age children. Gamification is one of the most highly accepted components among children with asthma, as it provides a positive user experience. The InspirerMundi app monitors inhaler adherence and offers a reward system using virtual badges (Jácome et al. 2021). ASTHMAXcel Adventures is an application designed for pediatric asthma patients (Hsia et al. 2020). AirPet is another gamified app that uses egg hatching to display indoor air quality (Kim et al. 2021). In the future, three-dimensional models and holograms could also be integrated to improve educational outcomes for children.

The global population is aging, and an increasing number of older adults with asthma can be expected. As with pediatric apps, it is necessary to identify features that are most appropriate for older patients. These may include larger text, more easily recognizable colors on displays, and more reliable medication reminder systems.

A mobile application has been developed for individuals visiting areas with Blue-Green Solutions. This app records physical activity and vital signs using wearable devices and monitors physical, physiological, and emotional status in people with chronic diseases such as asthma (Gallos et al. 2022). Such mHealth app features could be successfully applied in health resorts and other populated areas where monitoring health status is necessary.

The K-12 Bioinformatics program implemented in the USA in 2019 aimed to educate high school teachers on measuring air pollution and relating results to asthma outcomes. This initiative raises the issue that future mHealth

Table 1. Proposal for new functionalities and features.

Feature N	Proposed by Hui et al. 2020	Additional functionalities
Feature 1	The data logging system is preferably customizable.	The customization, according to us, could be fingerprints, retina scanning, or face recognition. The latter concerns personal data protection (EC 2016).
Feature 2	The system helps users learn the correct peak flow and inhaler technique (e.g., image recognition on incorrect peak flow).	In our opinion, inhaler techniques are different for different asthma medicines, so it is important to ask for the inhaler type before education.
Feature 3	A simple weather information display system.	This is especially important for highly polluted regions or cities, according to us.
Feature 4	An alarm system for geographical areas currently experiencing frequent asthma exacerbations.	This feature should be related to national environmental protection systems and health information databases to be usable, in our opinion.
Feature 5	The digitized asthma action plan system, in addition, could be able to correlate patient logs and weather with their asthma status.	For us, it is important that the digital asthma action plan relates to pharmacies and physicians' offices to follow up on patient behavior.
Feature 6	The medication reminder for patients.	This feature, according to us, could also be used by pharmacists and physicians.
Feature 7	A consultation appointment booking system.	Connected with the pharmacy system too.
Feature 8	The repeat prescription ordering system.	It should be available for pharmacists and physicians too. In the case of a private health insurer, the system might also relate to the payer, according to us.
Feature 9	The emergency system.	Such a system should alarm not only the patient but also the physician.
Feature 10		Whenever possible, apply new functionalities with AI to assist asthma patients and physicians in disease management.

development will require more professionals with education and experience in biomedical informatics and data analysis (Diwadkar et al. 2021).

A limited number of articles discussed the possibility of connecting patient data with physicians. Examples include the Hailie, KagenAir, and Propeller interactive asthma apps, which offer a wide range of features (Kagen et al. 2019). In our opinion, next-generation asthma apps should be designed to allow physicians to receive timely information about patient status and therapy adherence. Indicators of poor adherence should be incorporated into mHealth apps and shared with clinicians. For example, frequent use of salbutamol is an indicator of insufficient asthma control.

Proposal for new or improved features of mHealth apps

Hui et al. (2020) discussed in detail the features they consider necessary for asthma mHealth apps. Their perspective is closely aligned with ours, and the features are listed following the authors' original structure, with several additional functionalities included (Table 1).

Discussion

In this review, we aimed to explore features that have not been included in previous studies but could help patients and clinicians in a self-management app. We tried to systematize all features that patients or clinicians consider important and to propose additional ones in order to improve patient services as much as possible. Every patient with access to a smartphone may use asthma apps, but for low-income families, the high cost of smartphones could be an obstacle (Kagen et al. 2019). When selecting or creating an asthma app, it is first necessary to define the purpose of the app, whether for monitoring asthma symptoms, medication management, education, or communication with healthcare professionals. Patients, caregivers, health professionals, and regulatory bodies have different interests and focus on different aspects of mobile medical app design (Kagen et al. 2019).

mHealth apps need to respond appropriately to the changes brought by the 21st century. The global population is increasing, more people are using mobile devices, and the threat of cyberattacks is growing. As more confidential data are generated through mHealth apps, privacy and security become central issues. A standard login system is no longer sufficient. Biometric data provide millions of unique combinations and represent the future of user identification. The use of fingerprint recognition via touch screens or iris identification captured by an app's camera could represent valuable features for login systems in mHealth apps.

Patients want access to educational videos and alerts when their disease is out of control, whereas caregivers are more interested in monitoring medication adherence data through an app (Kagen et al. 2019). When using an app, young people are often pleased to show their disease-related progress to their physicians and feel better prepared for communication during medical visits (Roberts et al. 2016). To achieve the necessary features of an mHealth asthma app, discussion and collaboration are required among patients, caregivers, health professionals, and other stakeholders involved in the development process. Our article provides useful insight into the available properties of asthma apps and ways to improve their usability for physicians, patients, and health authorities.

Most asthma-related apps are focused on education and training, including yoga postures, breathing exercises, and general or treatment-related information presented through videos and text. A smaller proportion of apps focus on symptom tracking and medication use (Wu et al. 2015). In our opinion, all apps that provide healthcare information should be tested and validated by healthcare specialists.

With the increasing number of apps available on the open market, mHealth app quality has become an issue of major importance. The Asthma Control Test (ACT[®]) and the Mobile Asthma Severity Test (MAST[®] test) are validated outcome measures used in asthma apps. In the absence of certified standards, app quality was previously difficult to assess objectively. However, with the development of the Mobile App Rating Scale (MARS), the overall quality of apps can now be evaluated (Kagen et al. 2019). According to research-

ers, leading interactive apps with high MARS scores include Hailie, KagenAir, and Propeller Health (Kagen et al. 2019).

Some authors place strong emphasis on the validation and certification of medical apps, which we also consider to be of critical importance for patient safety. Active medical review may represent one step toward ensuring the safety of apps entering the market (Wicks et al. 2015). In this context, we believe that regulatory changes are necessary so that mobile apps containing health-related information and advice for patients are classified as medical devices and subject to certification. Although other control mechanisms may be applied, the health information presented within apps should be validated, and the platform or device should be certified by medical specialists.

Our study has several limitations, including the fact that only the PubMed database was searched. Other relevant apps may exist but were not captured in this review. Another limitation is that we analyzed only mHealth apps available in English. However, we acknowledge that some apps in other languages were identified (Munteanu et al. 2019; Munteanu et al. 2020; Al-Nawayseh et al. 2021; Salim et al. 2021; Al Raimi et al. 2022; van den Berg et al. 2022; Versteegh et al. 2022; Pohan et al. 2024; Zijp et al. 2024).

Conclusion

Mobile health apps can help patients manage their asthma more effectively. To create highly functional apps, dialogue is required between app developers and all other stakeholders involved in the development process. The features identified as most promising include the integration of low-cost sensors for monitoring patient status and remote consultation capabilities, which can bring health-care services to remote locations.

Improving health and digital literacy will not only increase the adoption of these technologies but also allow knowledge to be integrated into daily life. Personalization of mHealth apps increases user motivation for sustained use over time. Certification and quality control are also essential aspects of mHealth apps, without which appropriate

development direction cannot be ensured. Most importantly, mHealth apps and wearable technologies will lay the foundation for next-generation technologies in the future.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study was funded by the European Union Next-Generation EU through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project N BG-RRP 2.004-0004-C01.

Author contributions

Both authors contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Petar Nikolov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5896-4270>

Guenka Petrova <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8116-5138>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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